

REVIEW

Ultrathin ionic liquid films on metal surfaces: adsorption, growth, stability and exchange phenomena

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ABSTRACT

The interface of ionic liquids (ILs) with solid surfaces is of pivotal interest for many applications, ranging from sensors, lubrication, separation technology, and electronics to electrochemistry and catalysis. We present a short review on ultrathin layers of ionic liquids on metal surfaces using a surface science approach. We mainly focus on specific examples of imidazolium-based ionic liquids on Ag(111) and Au(111) studied by angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, and relate the obtained results to existing literature. We address a variety of phenomena on the molecular level, namely, (i) the adsorption, growth and wetting behavior of ILs, (ii) the thermal stability and desorption of ILs, (iii) exchange processes of anions and cations at the IL/solid interface, and (iv) the replacement of ILs from the IL/solid interface by porphyrins.

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Introduction

Ionic liquids (ILs) are a diverse and fascinating class of materials. As salts with comparably low melting points – often even below room temperature (RT) – they combine typically very low vapor pressures with a large number of tunable chemical and physicochemical properties, depending on the numerous possible pairings of cations and anions [1–13]. One of the most successful applications involving bulk amounts of ILs is the BASIL™ process for the production of alkoxyphenylphosphines [14,15]. The increasing realization of the incredible potential of task-specific ILs goes along with a continuously growing interest in the interfaces of IL systems.

IL interfaces are particularly important for interface-controlled applications such as sensor [4,16–19], lubrication [20–22], separation [4,19,23–29], electrochemistry [4,19,30–39] and electronics [40–42] technologies. ILs further stimulated completely new concepts for catalysis [1,4,43–57]. Thin IL films on high-surface-area solid supports are the key ingredient to highly effective SCILL [52] (Solid Catalyst with Ionic Liquid Layer) and SILP [25,44,49] (Supported Ionic Liquid Phase) catalysis. The groundbreaking discovery in SCILL, for example, was the ability of the IL phase to make the reactive sites of a heterogeneous catalyst more resistant towards poisoning while simultaneously increasing the reactivity and selectivity [52,58–60]. The examples in Figure 1 highlight the fundamental interest in liquid/solid and liquid/gas interfaces and some of the applications mentioned above [11,57,61–65]. The low vapor pressure and excellent thermal stability of many ILs enable not only their use under extreme conditions, but also their investigation in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) under well-defined conditions with atomic level accuracy [11,66], coining the term ‘Ionic Liquid Surface Science’ as a pivotal sub-discipline of IL research [11] and initiating a new age for the spectroscopic investigation of liquid surfaces in general [7,11,63,67].

IL/solid interfaces buried under macroscopically thick IL films are not accessible to most of the sophisticated UHV surface science methods[11]. After the successful distillation of ILs at reduced pressure without decomposition[68], the first use of physical vapor deposition of ILs (IL-PVD) in 2008 [69,70] combined with angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (ARXPS) led the way to establishing powerful new approaches for studying IL/solid and IL/vacuum interfaces of ultrathin IL films. The investigations with molecular resolution include the wetting behavior and IL film growth under well-controlled and ultraclean conditions for coverages ranging from the sub-monolayer range to several multilayers [11,63,69,71–79].

In the following, we review a number of studies addressing the adsorption, growth and stability of ultrathin films of ILs or IL mixtures on metal surfaces, which were obtained mostly by IL-PVD and ARXPS. In addition,

Figure 1. Pioneering works and substantial reviews highlight the fundamental interest in liquid/solid and liquid/gas interfaces in general [10,63,66,67] and the relevance of ionic liquid interfaces for applications [11,20,21,31,52,135,199,200]. The function, performance and stability of the applied systems strongly rely on the interface properties [11,57,61–65].

results obtained by other experimental techniques are included where appropriate. We concentrate mostly on specific examples for a narrow group of imidazolium-based ILs (Table 1) on single-crystalline Ag(111) and Au(111) surfaces. For these systems, a comprehensive data set is available, which serves as basis for a detailed comparison. The chosen examples also demonstrate the level of insight, which can be achieved for specific systems. Where possible, we deduce general trends. We mainly refer to data from our own group, because they represent the largest available set of data, and are obtained under identical experimental conditions. This allows for cross-correlating results in different chapters. In addition, we also compiled a comprehensive overview of literature data from other surface science studies of ILs on metal surfaces, concerning adsorption and growth of ultrathin IL layers (Table 2) and desorption of ILs (Table 3).

More specifically, we will address the following questions: How do IL/solid interfaces form? How do the ions arrange at the interfaces? How do the initial stages of thin film growth depend on the chemical nature of IL and support, and how stable are the ultrathin IL films at elevated temperatures [71,74,76,78,80–83]. We further extend the scope by looking at mixtures of ILs on metal surfaces on the nanoscale. Such systems promise an even larger

Table 1. Names, molecular structures and further details of the compounds discussed in this review. The entries shaded in gray are discussed in detail in this work

Short name	Molecular structure and IUPAC name	Glass transition ^a T_g [K]	Melting point ^a T_m [K]	Surface tension σ [mN/m]	Density ρ [g/cm ³]	Molecular volume V_m [nm ³]	Monolayer height ^b h [nm]
[C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N]	 1,3-dimethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethyl)sulfonylimide	-	295 ^[201] 299 ^[146]	36.3 ^{f,[8]}	1.554 ^{f,[146]} 1.567 ^{f,[8]}	0.400 ^{f,[8]}	0.73 ^[71,76,80,86]
[C₂C₁Im][Tf₂N]	 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethyl)sulfonylimide	178 ^[202] 180 ^[203] 181 ^[204] 186 ^[146] 195 ^[205]	252 ^[205] 254 ^[206] 255 ^[146,203] 256 ^[204] 257 ^[202] 263 ^[207] 270 ^[201] 257–271 ^[149]	32.6 ^{f,[106]} 35.1 ^{f,[208]} 35.2 ^{f,[209,210]} 41.6 ^{f,[211]}	1.516 ^[212] 1.518 ^{f,[208]} 1.519 ^{f,[205]} 1.522 ^{f,[146]} 1.524 ^{g,[207]}	0.428 ^{f,[8,208]}	0.75
[C₄C₁Im][Tf₂N]	 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethyl)sulfonylimide	169 ^[2] 181 ^[151] 182 ^[147] 186 ^[146,202,205,213] 187 ^[204]	248 ^[2] 267 ^[205] 268 ^[206] 269 ^[147,201] 270 ^[146,213] 271 ^[204] 272 ^[202]	30.7 ^{f,[8]} 30.8 ^{f,[106]} 37.5 ^{f,[2]}	1.43 ^{f,[2,106]} 1.435 ^{f,[8]} 1.436 ^{f,[205]} 1.437 ^[212] 1.44 ^{f,[146,204]}	0.485 ^{f,[8]}	0.79 ^[74]
[C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N]	 1-methyl-1-(3-octyl)imidazolium bis(trifluoromethyl)sulfonylimide	185 ^[149] 187 ^[147,148] 189 ^[205] 193 ^[146]	250–264 ^[149]	29.5 ^{f,[8]} 30.2 ^{f,[214]} 30.4 ^[210]	1.31 ^{f,[8,147,215]} 1.32 ^{f,[205,214]} 1.322 ^{f,[146]} 1.325 ^[212]	0.598 ^d 0.603 ^{f,[8]} 0.62 ^[6]	0.84 ^[71,80,81]
[C₈C₁Im]Cl	 1-methyl-1-(3-octyl)imidazolium chloride	186 ^[2]	191 ^[150]	30.9 ^{f,[8]} 33.8 ^{f,[2]}	1.00 ^{f,[2,216]} 1.009 ^{f,[8]} 1.01 ^[6]	0.380 ^{f,[8]}	0.72 ^[87]

(Continued)

Table 1. (Continued).

Short name	Molecular structure and IUPAC name	Glass transition ^a T_g [K]	Melting point ^a T_m [K]	Surface tension σ [mN/m]	Density ρ [g/cm ³]	Molecular volume V_m [nm ³]	Monolayer height ^b h [nm]
[C ₂ C ₁ Im][TfO]	 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate	75 ^[203]	258 ^[203] 264 ^[201]	37.8 ^{f,[106]} 44.4 ^{f,[211]}	1.388 ^{g,[217]} 1.39 ^{f,[106]}	0.311 ^{g,[217]}	0.68 ^[78]
[PFBMIm][PF ₆]	 1-methyl-3-(3,3,4,4,4-pentafluorobutyl)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate	-	3	39 ^[82]		0.360 ^{h,[82]}	0.71 ^[82]
[C ₄ C ₁ Im][PF ₆]	 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate	189 ^[151] 193 ^[2] 196 ^[205,213] 197 ^[204] 212 ^[218]	212 ^[150] 284 ^[204] 282 ^[206] 283 ^[2,213]	47.9 ^{f,[211]} 48.8 ^{f,[2]}	1.31 ^{f,[216]} 1.360 ^{f,[2,219]} 1.368 ^{f,[205]}	0.345 ^e 0.347 ^{f,[219]}	0.70
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆]	 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate	91 ^[2] 194 ^[151] 202 ^[205]	203 ^[150]	32.5 ^{f,[8]} 36.5 ^{f,[2]}	1.19 ^{f,[216]} 1.22 ^{f,[2,212,219]} 1.235 ^{f,[8]} 1.237 ^{f,[205]}	0.458 ^{f,[8]} 0.46 ^[6] 0.461 ^{f,[219]}	0.77 ^[81-83]
[C ₄ C ₁ Im][BF ₄]	 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate	176 ^[2] 178 ^[220] 182 ^[151] 188 ^[204] 190 ^[213] 192 ^[218] 190 ^[220] 193 ^[216]	192 ^[150,216]	46.6 ^{f,[2]}	1.12 ^{f,[2]} 1.205 ^[204] 1.26 ^{f,[216]}	0.312 ^[221]	0.68
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][BF ₄]	 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate		193 ^[150]	30.8 ^{f,[8]}	1.08 ^{f,[216]} 1.091 ^[219] 1.099 ^{f,[8]} 1.104 ^{f,[114]} 1.105 ^{f,[212,222]}	0.424 ^{f,[114]} 0.426 ^{f,[8]} 0.43 ^{f,[6,219]}	0.75 0.6 ^{c,[114]}

(Continued)

Table 1. (Continued).

Short name	Molecular structure and IUPAC name	Glass transition ^a T_g [K]	Melting point ^a T_m [K]	Surface tension σ [mN/m]	Density ρ [g/cm ³]	Molecular volume V_m [nm ³]	Monolayer height ^b h [nm]
[C ₄ C ₁ Pyrr][Tf ₂ N]	 N-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethylanesulfonyl)imide	181 ^[223] 186 ^[202,223]	252 ^[223] 255 ^[202] 262 ^[223] 264 ^[206] 267 ^[207]	32.3 ^{f,[8]}	1.39 ^[212] 1.394 ^{f,[8]} 1.399 ^{g,[207]}	0.503 ^{f,[8]}	0.80
[C ₄ C ₁ Pyrr][FAP]	 N-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium tetrakis(pentafluoroethyl)arsofluorophosphate	157 ^[224]	277 ^[224]	38 ^{g,[224]}	1.59 ^[212]	0.613 ^[212]	0.85
ZH-TTP	 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin	-	-	-	1.273 ^[225,226]	-	0.34 ^{c,[83]}

a: Can depend strongly on heating rate, thermal history (e.g. cooling rate) or water content [2,146,148,149,208,215,223]. Some studies suggest different temperatures for melting of organized domains at and below monolayer coverage on metal surfaces [73,91,94,130] and even for multilayers [70,114].

b: For details on the calculation of h see the Experimental Section.

c: Value determined experimentally.

d: Based on literature data [214].

e: Based on literature data [227].

f: At 298 K.

g: At 293 K.

Table 2. Overview over selected molecular level studies of IL thin film growth and structure at IL/metal interfaces. The entries shaded in gray are discussed in detail in this work.

Ionic Liquid	Surface	WL	Multilayer	Remarks ^a	Ref.
[C ₄ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Ag(111)	Yes	3D	ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT. Time-dependent changes of film morphology at RT.	[80]
	Au(111)	Yes	2D	ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT.	[71]
	Ni(111)	Yes	3D	ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at 220 K. Sandwich arrangement of ion pairs in WL.	[86]
	Ag(111), Au(111)	Yes	-	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at < 120 K.	[94]
[C ₂ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Au(110)	Yes	3D	STM at 128 K, LEED and UPS at RT, surface reconstruction upon IL adsorption. Time-dependent changes of film morphology at RT.	[91]
	Ni(111)	Yes	-	TOF-SIMS at 150 to 280 K.	[70]
[C ₄ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Au film on mica	Yes	3D	Pulsed-valve deposition. XPS and <i>ex-situ</i> AFM at RT.	[132]
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Ag(111)	Yes	3D	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at < 120 K, ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT. Interaction with co-adsorbed [C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆].	[80,94]
	Au(111)	Yes	2D	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at < 120 K and RT. ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT, study of beam damage.	[71,79,87,94]
	Cu(100)	Yes	-	STM for WL coverage and XPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT. STM showed no clear order in the WL at RT.	[79]
[C ₈ C ₁ Im]Cl	Au(111)	Yes	3D	ESI deposition. ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers and <i>ex-situ</i> AFM on multilayers at RT.	[87]
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆]	Ag(111), Au(111)	Yes	3D	ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT and < 90 K. Interaction with co-adsorbed porphyrin layer, [C ₈ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N] and [PFBMIm][PF ₆].	[81–83]
[C ₄ C ₁ Im][BF ₄]	Pt on Al ₂ O ₃	Yes	2D	Nano-inkjet printing. AFM at RT indicates 2D growth up to 4 nm.	[228]
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][BF ₄]	Cu(111)	Yes	3D	XPS and UPS at 120 K and RT. The film morphology changes upon heating to RT after deposition at 120 K.	[114]
[PFBMIm][PF ₆]	Ag(111)	Yes	3D	ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT. Interaction with co-adsorbed [C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆].	[82]
[C ₂ C ₁ Im][TfO]	Au(111)	Yes	3D	ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT. Growth is closer to 2D on partially Pd-covered Au(111).	[78]
	Pd(111)	Yes	-	IRAS on WL and multilayers. At 220 K, checkerboard arrangement in first layer. Strong interaction of the anion with the metal influences multilayer structure.	[125,126]
[C ₄ C ₁ Pyrr][Tf ₂ N]	Ag(111)	Yes	-	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at < 120 K.	[119]
	Au(111)	Yes	2D	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at < 120 K. ARXPS for sub-monolayer to multilayers at RT.	[73,119]
	Cu(111)	Yes	-	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at 100 K and RT.	[75]
[C ₄ C ₁ Pyrr][FAP]	Au(111)	Yes	-	STM for sub-monolayer coverage at 210 K and RT. Not clear, whether checkerboard or sandwich arrangement in WL.	[129]

a: IL films prepared by PVD, if not indicated otherwise.

Table 3. Desorption temperatures T_{des} of selected ILS on metal surfaces in comparison to values for activation energy of multilayer desorption E_a , enthalpy of vaporization ΔH_{vap} at 298 K and vapor pressure p_{sat} at 423 K (errors in the least significant figure in round brackets). β : Heating rate of the desorption experiment. The entries shaded in gray are discussed in detail in this work.

Ionic Liquid	Surface	T_{des} [K] (WL)	T_{des} [K] (Multilayer)	β [K/min]	E_a [kJ/mol] (Multilayer)	ΔH_{vap} [kJ/mol]	p_{sat} [μPa]	Remarks	Ref.
[C ₁ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Ag(111)	425	345	2	118 ^a	-	-	TP-XPS.	b
	Ni(111)	< 400	< 400	-	-	-	-	IL desorbs entirely upon heating to 400 K.	[86]
[C ₂ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Au(111)	380–500	380	30	118(2) ^[88]	134(2) ^[88]	1280 ^[140]	TPD; broad range for WL desorption.	[92]
	Au(110)	> 520	~370	10	126 ^[92]	137(5) ^[92]	-	TD-UPS; IL covered Au(110) surface undergoes reconstruction from 1 × 1 to 1 × 3 upon heating > 490 K.	[91]
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][Tf ₂ N]	Ag(111)	425	365	2	126 ^a 131(2) ^[88]	149(2) ^[88]	380 ^[140]	TP-XPS; WL desorption shifts to < 370 K after replacement by [C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆] at Ag(111) surface.	[81]
	Au(111)	> 400	< 400	-	-	-	-	Multilayers desorb upon heating to 400 K for 10 min while the WL remains.	[79]
	Cu(100)	> 400	< 400	-	-	-	-	Multilayers desorb upon heating to 400 K for 10 min while the WL remains. XPS indicates stronger interaction of IL WL with Cu(100) than Au(111).	[79]
[C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆]	Ag(111)	445	405	2	139 ^a 143(4) ^[88]	169(4) ^[88]	8 ^[140]	TP-XPS; WL desorption shifts to < 420 K on 2H-TPP-covered Ag(111).	[81–83]
	Au(111)	445	405	2	167 (18) ^[83]	-	-	TP-XPS; WL desorption shifts to < 420 K on 2H-TPP-covered Au(111).	[83]
	Au(111)	> 400	> 400	30	137(3) ^[88]	157 ^[221] 162(3) ^[88]	12 ^[140]	TPD; same temperature for multilayer and WL desorption.	[229,230]
	Cu(111)	> 460	420	-	-	-	-	TP-XPS; decomposition of WL before desorption is suggested.	[114]
[PF ₆ Im][PF ₆]	Ag(111)	-	390	2	148 ^a	-	-	TP-XPS; cation decomposes in WL above 420 K. WL desorption shifts to < 420 K after replacement by [C ₈ C ₁ Im][PF ₆] at Ag(111) surface.	[82]
[C ₄ C ₁ Pyrr][Tf ₂ N]	Cu(111)	-	-	-	132(2) ^[212]	152(3) ^[212] 195(19) ^[231]	-	Anions in contact with Cu surface decompose below 300 K.	[75]

a: Redhead analysis [232] with frequency factor $\nu_1 = 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ from literature [92]; b: See Figure 7(a); TPD: Temperature-programmed desorption; TP-XPS: Temperature-programmed XPS; TP-UPS: Temperature-programmed ultra-violet photoelectron spectroscopy.

parameter space for targeted applications of ultrathin IL films [81] and raise an additional and whole new set of fundamental questions specifically for mixed thin films: Are there effects of preferential adsorption, segregation and enrichment at the IL/solid and at the IL/vacuum interface? What is the structure and composition at both interfaces? How do these phenomena relate to varying combinations of ions and how do they evolve with temperature? [81,82] Finally, we address exchange processes between IL ions and larger aromatic molecules such as porphyrins at metal/liquid interfaces.

Experimental

Materials

The compounds relevant for this review are listed in Table 1 along with selected properties. The table also shows a selection of other ILs that were not studied here, but will be mentioned in the discussion.

The round Ag(111) and Au(111) single crystals (MaTecK) with a diameter of 15 mm and a thickness of 2 mm had a purity of 99.999% and one side polished and aligned to the (111) plane with an accuracy better than 0.1° . They were mounted to Mo sample holders and fixed with Ta wires. Temperatures were measured using type K thermocouples inserted into a pinhole ($\varnothing = 0.3$ mm) at the side of the crystals. Surface preparation was done in UHV by sputtering with 600 eV Ar^+ ions followed by annealing at 800 K. Sample cleanliness and long range order were checked by XPS and low energy electron diffraction (LEED), respectively [80–82]. Ag(111) and Au(111) show low reactivity towards the ILs and 2H-TPP, and no changes in the atomic structure of these surfaces were reported upon deposition of these compounds [80,84,85].

Angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Using the full potential of ARXPS, we can extract depth-dependent quantitative chemical information from ultrathin films up to thicknesses of 10 nm. We can identify the chemical state of the atoms in the IL via XPS chemical shifts, investigate the adsorption geometries, and extract information on the growth behavior during the initial stages of film formation. In ARXPS, the surface sensitivity varies with electron emission angle (Figure 2): Measurements at normal emission ($\vartheta = 0^\circ$) probe the near-surface region with an information depth (ID) of 7–9 nm, depending on the kinetic energy; measurements at grazing emission ($\vartheta = 80^\circ$) probe the topmost surface layers, with an ID of 1–1.5 nm. The ID is defined as $3 \cdot \lambda \cdot \cos(\vartheta)$, with the inelastic mean free path λ of the electron in a material at a given kinetic energy. 95% of the measured signal originates from the ID . The surface

sensitivity at 80° is a factor of six higher than at 0° and thus allows for deriving information on the surface composition and on the arrangement of the molecules in the topmost layer. An increased signal at 80° as compared to 0° indicates an enrichment of this element in the topmost layers as compared to the bulk; correspondingly, a decreased signal at 80° indicates a depletion of this element.

Most of the experimental data presented in this review were obtained using a two-chamber UHV system for preparation (sputtering, annealing, PVD of ILs and 2H-TPP, LEED, QMS) and analysis (ARXPS), with a base pressure of about 5×10^{-11} mbar. ARXP spectra at 0° and 80° were acquired

Figure 2. Depth sensitivity of angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (ARXPS). (a) Photoelectrons are emitted from the sample upon X-ray irradiation. The information depth ID of $3 \cdot \lambda \cdot \cos \vartheta$ varies with the detection angle ϑ : for $\vartheta = 0^\circ$ ID is 6–9 nm, and for $\vartheta = 80^\circ$ ID is 1–1.5 nm, depending on the kinetic energy. (b) Side view of a $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ film scaled to ARXPS electron attenuation (molecular dynamics snapshot, J.N. Canongia Lopes, private communication). (c) Exponential decay of the contribution to the measured XPS signal for $\vartheta = 0^\circ$ (black) and $\vartheta = 80^\circ$ (red), for C 1s electrons with $\lambda(C\ 1s) = 2.8$ nm. Notably, the topmost layer (shaded in light blue) contributes $\sim 82\%$ to the measured signal at 80° and only 25% at 0° .

by rotating the sample, using a non-monochromated Al K α X-ray source (SPECS XR 50, 1486.6 eV, 240 W) and a hemispherical electron analyzer (VG SCIENTA R3000). All spectra were measured with a pass energy of 100 eV, which resulted in an overall energy resolution of ~ 0.9 eV. For more details, including peak fitting and background subtraction see Refs [72,77,80]. For temperature-programmed XPS, the sample was heated continuously during the measurements at a rate of 2 K/min. Due to the low thickness of the investigated films, we did not observe any signs of charging. However, beam damage can be an issue after long exposure to X-rays[71]. To avoid undesired effects, each film was freshly prepared by PVD on the clean metal surface after complete removal of the previous film by heating, sputtering and annealing.

Physical vapor deposition of ionic liquids and porphyrins

We deposited well-defined amounts of the different ILs (or porphyrins) via PVD using two special effusion cells optimized for IL-PVD (see Supporting Information of Ref. [81]): The cell design effectively prevents ILs (which tend to creep out of the crucible) from direct contact with the hot filaments, which would cause decomposition and possible contaminations on the target. A type K thermocouple is contacted to the bottom of the crucible to ensure an accurate temperature reading. The flux was checked using a quartz crystal microbalance to ensure stable and reproducible evaporation rates. To remove volatile impurities, the compounds were thoroughly degassed in UHV for more than 24 hours at elevated temperatures close to the respective evaporation conditions [71,78,81–83,86,87]. During deposition, the chamber background pressure was typically around 1×10^{-9} mbar. Most alkylimidazolium ILs evaporate intact in the form of neutral ion pairs [69,71,79–82,86,88–95]. The XP spectra of the thin films were compared to spectra of macroscopically thick IL films prepared *ex-situ*, and no indications of decomposition were observed [80–83].

Monitoring thin film growth with XPS

The growth of IL and porphyrin films on Ag(111) and Au(111) was monitored through changes of the substrate XPS signals (Ag 3d and Au 4f, respectively) at emission angles of $\vartheta = 0^\circ$ and 80° . For homogeneous two-dimensional (2D) growth, the substrate signal intensities at an angle ϑ decreases from I_0 for the clean surface, to I_d for a homogeneous film of thickness d according to [71,80–82,86,96,97]:

$$\frac{I_d}{I_0} = e^{-\frac{d}{\lambda \cdot \cos \vartheta}} \quad (1)$$

Notably, for ideal layer-by-layer growth (that means the full completion of a layer is achieved before a new layer starts to grow on top) the substrate signals should decrease in a section-wise linear fashion for each layer [71,80,86,96,97]. The statistics of the data presented here are, however, typically not good enough to unequivocally resolve such slope changes between adjacent straight sections.

In order to detect deviations from 2D film growth, a specific data representation is used mostly: the mean film thickness d for a given deposition experiment was calculated from the experimental I_d/I_0 ratios at $\vartheta = 0^\circ$, that is, in the bulk-sensitive emission geometry, according to Equation (1) [71,80–83]. With the obtained d value, the expected attenuation at $\vartheta = 80^\circ$, that is, in the surface-sensitive emission, was then calculated using the same equation. While agreement between the experimental data at 80° and the calculation at 80° indicates 2D growth, experimental I_d/I_0 ratios above the calculated curve indicate deviations towards a three-dimensional (3D) morphology of the IL film [96]; such behavior was observed for a number of systems [74,76,78,80–83,86]. At this point, one should mention that this approach works well, if the growth mode is 2D or moderate 3D. Then, the estimation of the average film thickness, that is, the deposited amount of IL as determined from the 0° data is reasonably accurate (e.g., the signals for a surface covered with one layer or half-covered with a double layer differ only by less than 2%). However, for pronounced 3D growth, the average thickness cannot be determined from the 0° data, due to strong self-damping in the islands. In such cases, the growth mode can be identified by plotting the obtained signal vs. time, as it is conventionally done [97]. This approach is however, sensitive to changes in the sticking coefficient or fluctuations/changes in the evaporator flux.

Estimation of the IL monolayer height

Throughout this review, IL coverages are given in the unit ‘ML’, where 1 ML represents an *ion pair* monolayer, that is, a closed double layer of ions irrespective of their relative arrangement [69,80–83,92]. Following this definition, a wetting layer (WL) with one closed layer of cations and anions adsorbed on the metal surface next to each other in a checkerboard-like structure corresponds to 0.5 ML. The monolayer height h (of 1 ML) is approximated as the cubic root of the molecular volume V_m based on mass density ρ values of the IL from literature [71,80–82,86]:

$$h = \sqrt[3]{V_m} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{M/N_A}{\rho}} \quad (2)$$

with M molar mass and N_A Avogadro constant[8]. According to this relation, h is 0.73 nm for $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, 0.84 nm for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, and 0.77 nm for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ using RT values for V_m from literature (see Table 1) [8,80,81]. The monolayer height h of $[PFBMIm][PF_6]$ with a so far unexplored mass density was estimated to be 0.71 nm, by comparison to the values for the non-fluorinated $[C_xC_1Im][PF_6]$ ILs (calculated from known mass densities), considering the increase of V_m upon replacing hydrogen by fluorine[98].

Monolayers of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) and Au(111) are prepared by multilayer deposition and subsequent heating to 500 K, that is, above the multilayer desorption temperature [83,99]. From the attenuation of the substrate XPS signal in 0° emission, the height of the monolayer of flat lying 2H-TPP molecules was calculated to 0.34 nm[83]. Notably, the spectra of monolayer 2H-TPP films obtained by multilayer desorption at 500 K showed no difference compared to films of similar thickness prepared by direct deposition at RT[83].

Results

Adsorption and growth behavior of ionic liquid thin films on metal surfaces

Understanding the interaction of ILs with solid supports is essential for thin film applications such as SILP or SCILL catalysis[11]. Of particular interest are the structure and arrangement of the ions at the liquid/solid interface, the initial stages of thin film growth, and ultimately the wetting behavior of thin IL films on the solid supports at room temperature (RT) [11,57,63,67,80]. A good wettability of the IL film is a crucial requirement for the performance of IL/catalyst composite systems [11,57]. While wetting of ILs has been studied quite extensively on the macroscopic and mesoscopic scale, mostly by contact angle measurements and atomic force microscopy (AFM) [10,57,100–113], only a few studies are available on the molecular scale [10,69,71,73,74,76,78,86,87,91,114–118].

In the following, we will focus on the behavior of four model systems, which are also relevant for the studies on IL mixtures and on IL exchange phenomena at the IL/support interface presented in the next chapters. These four model ILs are $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$, and $[PFBMIm][PF_6]$ (see Table 1). They were studied on Ag(111) and Au(111) by ARXPS. The main differences between the selected ILs are the different length and chemical composition of the alkyl chain at the imidazolium head group and the nature of the counter ion.

Adsorption and molecular arrangement of ionic liquids in the first layer

In Figure 3(a), the C 1s spectra for [C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] films of increasing thickness are displayed, from sub-ML coverage to multilayers; also shown are spectra of a macroscopic film prepared *ex situ* (topmost spectrum), and of the clean Ag(111) surface[80]. All spectra were acquired at 80° emission angle at RT. The C_{hetero} signal at ~287 eV is assigned to the five carbon atoms in the imidazolium cation bound to the hetero atom nitrogen, and the C_{anion} signal at ~293 eV to the two carbon atoms in the CF₃ groups of the [Tf₂N]⁻ anion, see Table 1. For coverages below 0.5 ML, the ratio of C_{anion} to C_{hetero} signal in Figure 3(b) is around 0.7, which is considerably larger than the nominal ratio of 2:5 = 0.4. This observation is attributed to a specific adsorption geometry of the ions in a checkerboard-like structure, with cations and anions next to each other in direct contact with the substrate (see Figure 4(a)). In this so-called wetting layer (WL), the imidazolium head groups lie parallel to the metal surface and the larger anions adsorb with *cis* conformation in an upright geometry with both CF₃ groups pointing away from the surface. Since the latter extend farther away from the surface, they attenuate the signal of the cations at 80° [71,80]. Investigations by low-temperature scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) of similar ILs confirm this highly ordered adsorption geometry up to 0.5 ML [94,119], where the surface is completely covered by the checkerboard structure. At higher coverages, the C_{anion}:C_{hetero} ratio gradually decreases to ~0.47 at 1.5 ML. This behavior is also characteristic for macroscopic films of this IL [6,71,80,86], and is assigned to a preferential orientation of the anions at the IL/vacuum interface with their CF₃ groups pointing towards the vacuum side.

Next, we address the adsorption of [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N], a similar IL with an octyl chain instead of one of the methyl groups; see Figure 4. The main difference in the C 1s spectra compared to the previous IL is the additional signal at ~285 eV, which is attributed to the seven C_{alkyl} carbon atoms of the octyl chain; see Figure 3(c). The C_{alkyl}:C_{hetero} ratio shows characteristic changes with increasing film thickness, see Figure 3(d). The ratio of ~1.6 at coverages < 0.5 ML is close to the nominal ratio of 1.4 (= 7:5), which indicates that the cation is adsorbed with both ring and alkyl chain lying flat on the surface. In this way, the interaction with the substrate is maximized. At ~0.5 ML, the C_{alkyl}:C_{hetero} ratio changes quickly to a value of ~2.9, which is attributed to a pronounced surface enrichment of the alkyl chains, leading to an attenuation of the C_{hetero} signal. This enrichment is even more pronounced than for thick films, where a ratio of ~2.25 is observed [6,71,80,86,120]. The shift of the C_{alkyl} peak by +0.5 eV to higher binding energies between 0.4 ML and 0.6 ML coverage reflects the decreased efficiency of core hole screening due to the detachment of the chains from the Ag(111) surface.

Figure 3. C 1s spectra in 80° emission for IL films of increasing thickness on Ag(111), prepared by PVD at RT, and for macroscopic (thick) films. $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$: (a) After completion of the wetting layer, the C_{hetero} peak shifts by about $+0.3$ eV while the C_{anion} peak shows no notable shift. (b) Ratio of the C_{anion} to C_{hetero} peak area as a function of the film thickness. The horizontal lines mark the nominal ratio ($2:5 = 0.4$) and the ratio observed for macroscopic films in 80° emission (0.47) [6,71,80,86]. The deviations for the thick film from the nominal ratio are due to a preferential surface enrichment of the CF_3 groups of the anion. $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$: (c) Towards the completion of the WL, the C_{alkyl} and C_{hetero} peaks shift by about $+0.5$ eV as a function of coverage while the C_{anion} peak appears to remain almost unshifted. (d) Ratios of the C_{alkyl} to C_{hetero} peak area as a function of the film thickness. The deviations for the thick films from the nominal ratio are due to a preferential surface enrichment of the alkyl chain of the cation. The horizontal lines mark the nominal ratio ($7:5 = 1.4$) and the ratio observed for macroscopic films in 80° emission (2.25) [6,71,80,86,120]. Adapted from [80] under license CC BY-NC 3.0 – Published by the PCCP Owner Societies.

Figure 4. Sketch of the IL arrangement at different coverages: (a) In the sub-wetting layer (<math><0.5\text{ ML}</math>) both ILs adsorb in a checkerboard structure with flat-lying imidazolium cations and the [Tf₂N]⁻ anions oriented such that the CF₃ groups point towards the vacuum side. For [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N], the octyl chain also lies flat on the surface, to maximize the interaction with the substrate. (b) In the saturated wetting layer ($=0.5\text{ ML}$), the cationic and anionic headgroups are packed densely and completely cover the surface; for [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N], the octyl chain is detached from the surface and points toward the vacuum, thereby creating space for more cations and anions to be adsorbed directly on the surface. (c) At higher coverages ($>1.5\text{ ML}$), the situation at the surface of a bulk IL is approached. Adapted in part from [80] under license CC BY-NC 3.0 – Published by the PCCP Owner Societies.

A similar behavior was observed for [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Au(111)[71], and also for [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] on Ag(111) and Au(111)[83]. The molecular rearrangement at $\sim 0.5\text{ ML}$ with the octyl chains bending away from the metal surface is attributed to the fact that it allows for a tighter packing of the ionic head groups within the wetting layer as sketched in Figure 4(b) [71,80]. Although this implies that the adsorption energy of the cation is lowered by the (missing) contribution of attractive van der Waals interactions of the alkyl chain with the support, it creates an energetic net benefit by decreasing the average lateral distance between the adsorbed ionic head groups, thereby freeing adsorption sites to adsorb further IL ion pairs in direct contact with the metal[83].

Independent of the length of the alkyl substituents at the imidazolium cation, the [Tf₂N]⁻ anion was found to adsorb on Ag(111) in a *cis* conformation with an upright orientation, with the oxygen atoms pointing towards the metal and the CF₃ groups away from the surface [80,81]. This geometry was observed previously for several ILs with [Tf₂N]⁻ as anion by ARXPS on Au(111) [71,73] and

by STM on Ag(111) [94,119], Au(111) [73,94,119], and other surfaces [75,76,121–124]. Notably, it was found at RT [71,73,76,80,81,121,123,124] and also at temperatures around 100 K [71,73,81,94,122]. Preferential orientation of the anion at the IL/metal interface was also reported by *in situ* IR spectroscopy for $[C_2C_1Im][TfO]$ on Pd(111) [125–127] and on Co-covered Pd(111)[128], such that the SO_3 group points towards the metal and the CF_3 group away from the surface.

Table 2 provides an overview over a range of molecular-level studies that deal with the adsorption and the initial film growth at IL/metal interfaces. The formation of a 2D WL with a checkerboard arrangement of (on average) alternating anions and cations is found in the majority of molecular-level studies [69–71,73–76,78,80–83,87,94,103,118,119,125,126,129–132]. One exception is $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ on Ni(111) at 220 K, where a sandwich-type arrangement was reported for coverages below 0.5 ML, with the $[C_1C_1Im]^+$ cation in contact with the surface and the $[Tf_2N]^-$ anion sitting on top of the cation[86].

IL growth and wetting behavior

The growth behavior of the ILs from the submonolayer to the multilayer range was characterized by measuring the attenuation of the substrate core level signal upon varying the IL coverage. As exemplary cases, we show the attenuation of the Au 4f and Ag 3d signals as a function of mean IL film thickness for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ on Au(111) and Ag(111) in Figure 5(a,b), respectively. As described in the Experimental Section, the mean film thickness d was calculated from the substrate signal attenuation in 0° ; from this thickness, the attenuation in 80° was calculated for ideal 2D layer-by-layer growth (dashed lines). Deviations of the measured 80° intensity from this ideal line then indicate a 3D morphology – the stronger the deviation the more pronounced the effect. Up to 0.5 ML, the good agreement of the 80° data with the calculated curves for 2D growth (dashed lines) confirms the formation of a closed molecular layer at both IL/substrate interfaces. In this wetting layer both cations and anions adsorb in the above mentioned checkerboard arrangement[80].

The growth behavior on top of the closed WL with a coverage of 0.5 ML depends on the substrate. For $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ and also $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ (not shown) on Au(111)[71], the 80° data in Figure 5(a) continue to follow the prediction for 2D layer-by-layer growth as sketched in Figure 6(a). In contrast, the 80° data for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ on Ag(111) above 0.5 ML in Figure 5(b) systematically falls above the 2D curve, indicating the formation of 3D islands on top of the WL; see Figure 6(b) (moderate 3D growth)[80]. This Stranski-Krastanov-like growth [133] (or pseudo partial wetting [134]) is also observed for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ on Ag(111) [82,83] and Au(111)[83], and other ILs

Figure 5. Dependence of the substrate signal (full symbols for 0° and open symbols for 80° emission) on IL film thickness for (a) $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Au(111), (b) $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Ag(111) and (c) $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ on Au(111). The solid and dashed lines show the exponential decay expected for 2D layer-by-layer growth for emission angles of 0° and 80° , respectively; they are calculated using Equation (1) with inelastic mean free paths λ of 3.0 nm for Au 4f and 2.5 nm for Ag 3d. For all systems, perfect agreement of the 80° data with the dashed line is found up to a coverage of 0.5 ML, indicating the formation of a complete wetting layer in each case. For $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Au(111), the 80° data exactly follow the dashed line also above 0.5 ML, which indicates continued 2D layer-by-layer growth (data adapted with permission from [71]. Copyright (2011) American Chemical Society). For $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Ag(111), the data points above 0.5 ML fall slightly above the prediction for 2D growth, indicating moderate 3D growth

on top of the wetting layer (data adapted from [80] under license CC BY-NC 3.0 – Published by the PCCP Owner Societies). For $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ on Au(111), a strong deviation from the ideal 2D behavior is evident for coverages above 0.5 ML, indicating pronounced 3D growth; note that due to this strong deviation, the average layer thickness here was determined via the deposition time. The green squares in (c) show the attenuation of Au 4f intensity after deposition of 23 Å $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ on Au(111) that was pre-covered with 1.6 Å (0.7 ML) Pd; the co-adsorbed Pd induces a pronounced change in growth behavior compared to the Pd-free surface (data adapted from [78] under license CC BY 3.0 – Published by the PCCP Owner Societies). For further details see text.

studied on clean metal surfaces (see Table 2) [78,80–83,86,87,114,131,132], and also on various other substrates [69,74,76,86,103,116,121,135]. Notably, the degree of deviation from perfect 2D behavior depends on the specific system. Studies on the mesoscopic scale also commonly report the formation of a 2D WL and subsequent droplet formation of ILs on a wide range of surfaces [101,102,104,105,108,109,111–113,136].

Presently, a molecular level understanding of the driving forces determining the detailed growth behavior on the wetting layer is missing. Clearly, it depends on the combination of a specific IL with a specific substrate, but no clear systematics is evident: An illustrative example of the diverse behavior is the comparison of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ on Au(111) in Figure 5(a,c), respectively. While for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ we observe more or less perfect 2D behavior, the data for $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$

Figure 6. Scheme of the initial stages of IL film growth observed on solid metal supports. Upon IL deposition initially always the formation of a 2D wetting layer is observed. The later stages can show (a) continued 2D growth, (b) moderate 3D growth, or (c) the pronounced 3D growth. Adapted in part from [80] under license CC BY-NC 3.0 – Published by the PCCP Owner Societies.

strongly deviate from the prediction for continued 2D growth above the wetting layer thickness, that is, the Au 4f signal stays nearly constant rather than decaying exponentially. This behavior is attributed to the formation of very pronounced 3D islands such as droplets covering only a fraction of the WL; see Figure 6(c)[78].

Most interestingly, this pronounced 3D growth of $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ on top the wetting layer on Au(111) can be switched by modifying the substrate: After pre- or postdeposition of only 0.7 Pd atoms per Au surface atom, a behavior close to 2D layer-by-layer growth (moderate 3D) is found, as is evident from the pronounced changes in Figure 5(c), indicated by vertical arrows. This change upon Pd deposition is attributed to strong attractive interactions between $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ and surface Pd. In turn, the strong interaction with the imidazolium cations stabilizes Pd at the metal surface. In the context of SCILL, these results provide a direct molecular level explanation for the beneficial influence of an IL layer in case of heterogeneous metal alloy catalysts[11].

The general observation of the formation of a WL for all ILs on metal substrates studied so far (see Table 2) is attributed to a strongly stabilizing interaction of the metal surface (as deduced from higher desorption temperatures of the WL compared to multilayers, see Chapter 3.2), by formation of image dipoles within the metal and possible (partial) charge transfer [92,118]. This interpretation is in line with conventional molecular scale interpretations of growth behavior in metal-organic heteroepitaxy [137,138].

In addition to studies on metals, there are also a few ARXPS investigations for other substrates. $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on glass grows in three-dimensional islands[69], and $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on freshly air-cleaved mica surfaces shows a pronounced dependence of the initial IL adsorption behavior on carbon precoverages: On clean mica, 3D growth (complete dewetting) occurs, whereas on a fully carbon-covered mica surface, initially a closed 2D wetting layer forms, followed by 3D growth[74]. The latter behavior is also observed on carbon substrates, more specifically, for $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) and on one layer of graphene on Ni(111))[76].

On the mesoscale, the concept of pseudo partial wetting for nonvolatile liquids is well known. Already in 1991, de Gennes *et al* [134]. published a model based on the liquid's surface tension to explain this wetting behavior for certain values of the parameters Hamaker constant A and spreading coefficient S . It remains to be shown, however, whether this model can be applied to ILs due to the limitations of this model considering long-range interactions [134] and the obvious Coulomb contributions to the intermolecular forces of ILs.

To conclude this chapter, the entirety of data currently available already allows for deriving some general conclusions. On the one hand, the

formation of a closed wetting layer on metal surfaces appears to be one general similarity for all ILs investigated so far. On the other hand, the successive IL growth on top of the wetting layer seems to depend on the detailed nature of the IL and the substrates. Small modifications can lead to considerable changes in the behavior, the origin of which is not understood yet. Consequently, there is still need for further data on a wider range of systems to allow for a clear correlation of film morphologies and IL/substrate properties.

Desorption of pure ILs from metal surfaces

While ILs commonly have very low vapor pressures at RT, thermal desorption can play a pivotal role for thin film applications at high temperature. Therefore, the maximum reaction temperatures of SCILL systems are not only limited by the thermal stability of the IL, but also by the desorption of the IL film from the support [11,139]. In the following, we will address the desorption of ILs from metals, as studied by temperature-programmed XPS (TP-XPS) [81–83]. The corresponding results are summarized in Table 3, complemented by further information from literature.

In Figure 7, we plotted the F 1s signal intensities of $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$, $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ [81] and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ [81,82] on Ag(111), along with the Ag 3d substrate signal, upon heating IL multilayer films to elevated temperatures (> 475 K). The observed behavior shows that all films desorb in two steps, that is, multilayers desorb first, followed by the desorption of the wetting layer. This behavior indicates that the ions in contact with the metal surface are bound more strongly than in the multilayer.

Comparing the desorption temperatures for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ [81] and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ [81–83] on Ag(111) in Figure 7(b,c), we note differences in the thermal stability, which originate from the different molecular compositions of the IL. More specifically, we find a higher desorption temperature for the multilayers and also the wetting layer for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ than for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ [81]. The higher temperature for multilayer desorption, where the interaction with the underlying metal plays a negligible role, is in line with literature values for the enthalpy of vaporization ΔH_{vap} and for the vapor pressure p_{sat} , see Table 3: $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ has a higher enthalpy of vaporization [88] and accordingly also a lower vapor pressure [140] than $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$. For the WL on Ag(111), the lower desorption temperature of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ compared to $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ indicates a stronger adsorption of the latter on the metal surface that likely results from the smaller size of the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion and thus a more localized charge which might induce a stronger image dipole within the metal.

The analysis of the behavior for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ on different substrates, Ag(111) and Au(111), shows that the multilayers desorb at identical

Figure 7. Thermal evolution of F 1s (F_{Tf_2N} (green), F_{PF_6} (blue)) and Ag 3d signal intensities at 0° emission from TP-XPS upon heating multilayer films of (a) $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, (b) $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ [81], and (c) $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ [81,82] on Ag(111). Heating rate: 2 K/min. The vertical arrows indicate the rate maxima of multilayer and WL desorption. The horizontal dashed lines indicate the intensity of the wetting layer as obtained upon adsorption at RT (for details see text).

temperatures (see Table 3), as is to be expected. Interestingly, we also find similar desorption temperatures for both wetting layers, indicating similar adsorption energies of this IL on both metals [83].

Next, we compare the behavior of the two ILs with the same anion, but different cations, $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ and $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ on Ag(111); see Figure 7(a,b). It was established previously that the enthalpy of vaporization of homologues of imidazolium-based $[C_nC_1Im]X$ ILs (with X: $[Tf_2N]$, $[TfO]$, $[BF_4]$) from macroscopic samples increases linearly with the number of C atoms in the alkyl chain (for $n = 2$ to 10) [140–142]. It seems therefore reasonable that also in thin films multilayers of $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ desorb at a lower temperature (345 K) than multilayers of $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ (365 K), as

shown in [Figure 7](#). Interestingly, the desorption temperatures of the respective WLs of the two ILs on Ag(111) are very similar, which leads us to suggest that the adsorption energy of the IL on the surface is mainly dominated by the interaction of the ionic head groups with the surface and that the length of the cation side chain has a only relatively small influence.

Notably, the residual F 1s intensity of the $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ WL on Ag(111) after the multilayer desorption, that is, above 375 K in [Figure 7\(b\)](#) is about 30% lower than for a WL obtained from direct deposition at RT (as indicated by the horizontal dashed line). A similar behavior is also observed for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ on Ag(111) and Au(111). For $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Ag(111), in contrast, the residual F 1s intensity of the WL after multilayer desorption exactly matches that of a WL from direct deposition. As described in Chapter 3.1, the alkyl chains of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ gradually detach and point away from the surface upon approaching WL coverage during the initial stages of film growth. One could imagine that the adsorption energy per molecule in this densely packed layer is lower than in the lower coverage phase. We thus propose that the WL partially desorbs (at temperatures similar to that of the multilayer), and that the alkyl chains of the remaining molecules in the (high temperature) WL assume a flat lying geometry on the Ag(111) surface. The lower coverage then is the consequence of the larger spatial requirement of the $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+$ cation in this adsorption geometry. This would also explain why $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$, in contrast, shows identical F 1s intensities in the WL after multilayer desorption and after direct WL deposition, because it lacks such an alkyl chain substituent.

There are a few other investigation addressing the thermal desorption of ILs from metal surfaces ([Table 3](#)). In a temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) study of $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Au(111), Hessey and Jones [92] observe a slightly higher multilayer desorption temperature of 380 K and a rather broad WL desorption range compared to the value of 365 K for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Ag(111) from TP-XPS[81]. Both differences are likely related to the much higher heating rate of the TPD experiment of 30 K/min [92] compared to the TP-XPS with 2 K/min [81,143,144]. The broad range for the WL desorption could also be a sign of decomposition of the $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ film on the Au surface.

Interestingly, the multilayer desorption temperature of 390 K for the partially fluorinated IL $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ on Ag(111) is close to the value of 405 K for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ on Ag(111)[82]. This observation indicates that the seemingly significant structural variation at the cation of these two ILs – which has a profound effect on the interface composition and enrichment behavior in mixed films [82,145] (see below) – has only little effect on the

multilayer desorption. For the WL of [PFBMIm][PF₆] on Ag(111), XPS clearly indicates decomposition of the IL above 420 K[82], in contrast to [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] on Ag(111), where no signs of decomposition are observed upon thermal desorption[83]. Thus, the adsorption energy of [PFBMIm][PF₆] cannot be deduced simply from TP-XPS because of the decomposition of the IL[82].

Ion exchange at the IL/solid interface

In this chapter, we discuss phenomena that occur in sequentially deposited ultrathin films of two different ILs on Ag(111). The results demonstrate that already well below RT ion exchange processes can occur at the IL/metal interface [81,82].

Anion exchange

We start with considering an IL system, where the two ILs have the same cation, but two different anions, that is, [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] and [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] [81]. Notably, the different chemical environments of the F_{Tf₂N} and F_{PF₆} atoms in the two anions result in distinct chemical shifts of the respective F 1s binding energies in XPS (~689 vs ~687 eV, respectively). This allows for a direct comparison of the relative occurrence of the respective anion in the bulk (0° emission) and at the surface (80°) of the IL films in the F 1s spectra in Figure 8. Changes in signal intensity by varying the surface sensitivity in ARXPS directly reflect surface enrichment or depletion of one of the anions [81,82].

In a first step, the equivalent of a WL of [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] was deposited on Ag(111) at 90 K (see sketch in Figure 9), resulting in one signal in the F 1s spectra in Figure 8(b). At this low temperature, STM [94] and ARXPS [81] indicate the formation of flat uniform films with crystalline and amorphous condensed phases, all with an overall checkerboard arrangement of alternating anions and cations. In a second step, 1.3 ML of [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] were deposited on top of the WL of [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] at 90 K, resulting in a strong attenuation of the F_{Tf₂N} signal at 80° in Figure 8(c), as [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] homogeneously covers the underlying [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] layer. As sketched in Figure 9(c), no exchange of anions occurs at this point[81].

This composite IL film was then heated to RT. The considerable increase of the F_{Tf₂N} signal at 80° together with the decrease of the F_{PF₆} signal in Figure 8(d) clearly shows that the [Tf₂N]⁻ anions resurfaced. The behavior is even more evident from the quantitative analysis of the TP-XPS data at 80° in Figure 8. Initially, there are no notable changes in the F_{PF₆} and F_{Tf₂N} peak intensities. Above 140 K, the F_{PF₆} signal (blue) begins to decrease, while the F_{Tf₂N} signal (green) remains constant up to 170 K. This behavior is attributed to a reorganization within the uppermost layer, such that the octyl

Figure 8. Top: F 1s spectra in 0° and 80° emission for (a) the clean Ag(111) crystal, (b) after deposition of a WL of $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ at 90 K, (c) after deposition of 1.3 ML of $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ on top of the $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ WL at 90 K, and (d) after heating the resulting composite IL film to RT. Bottom left: Intensities of the respective F 1s signals of the $[PF_6]^-$ and $[Tf_2N]^-$ anions from TP-XPS in 80° emission as a function of the sample temperature upon heating to RT. Bottom right: Molecular structures of the ILs. Adapted from [81] under license CC BY 4.0.

chains enrich at the IL/vacuum interface around 150 K and attenuate the F_{PF_6} signal at 80°, as sketched in Figure 9 (marked with *) [81]. Unaffected by this reorientation at the outer surface, the $[Tf_2N]^-$ anions remain at the IL/Ag(111) interface. Between 170 and 220 K, the exchange of the anions at the IL/Ag(111) interface occurs, as the F_{Tf_2N} signal increases while the F_{PF_6} signal continues to decrease [81]. The temperature range for the observed anion exchange corresponds well to glass transition temperatures of bulk

Figure 9. Scheme for the heating experiment after the deposition of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ on top of a WL of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Ag(111) at 90 K. The Roman numerals and asterisk refer to Figure 8. Adapted from [81] under license CC BY 4.0.

$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ (around 185 K [146–149] and 190 K [2,150,151], respectively)[81].

Two driving forces are proposed to be cooperatively responsible for the replacement of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ by $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at the IL/Ag(111) interface and the enrichment of $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]^-$ at the IL/vacuum interface. As deduced from the desorption temperatures of the neat ILs on Ag(111) (see Chapter 3.2) the adsorption energy of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ is considerably larger than that of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$. Furthermore, the preferential enrichment of $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]^-$ at

the IL/vacuum interface is favored because of the lower surface tension of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ compared to $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ (see Table 1) [8,81].

Cation exchange

Next, we address the exchange of two cations at the IL/Ag(111) interface, for a system with two different cations, but the same anion, namely, $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$. Similar to the previous example, the different chemical environments of the five F_{CFx} atoms in the side chain of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation and the six F_{PF_6} atoms in the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion result in distinct F 1s binding energies (F_{CFx} at 689.1 eV, F_{PF_6} at 686.9 eV) allowing for a direct comparison of the relative occurrence in the bulk (0° emission) and at the vacuum interface (80°) of the ultrathin films (Figure 10)[82].

For the detailed investigation of the dynamics of the cation exchange, first a WL of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, and in a second step 1.0 ML of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ were deposited at 82 K on Ag(111). ARXPS shows that $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ covers the WL of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and no ion exchange occurs at the IL/Ag(111) interface at this low temperature (lower two schemes of Figure 11(a))[82]. While heating this layered film with a rate of 2 K/min to RT, the thermal evolution of the F 1s and C 1s signals related to cations and anions was measured *in situ* in 80° emission. The quantitative analysis of the individual C 1s (C_{alkyl} and C_{hetero}) and F 1s (F_{CFx} and F_{PF_6}) signals is shown in Figure 10. Upon heating, a decrease of the F_{PF_6} signal (blue) is observed initially, while simultaneously the C_{alkyl} signal (yellow) increases until 150 K. These changes are again attributed to the enrichment of the alkyl chains at the IL/vacuum interface, which leads to the attenuation of the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anions below, similar to the observations above for the anion exchange. The alkyl enrichment by reorientation is limited to the IL/vacuum interface and there is no change of the F_{CFx} peak intensity (red) of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cations at the IL/Ag(111) interface. Between 160 and 220 K, the cations at the IL/Ag(111) interface undergo exchange, followed by the enrichment of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ at the vacuum interface at the expense of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+$ cations, as the F_{CFx} signal increases and the C_{alkyl} signal decreases[82].

The temperature range of the cation exchange again corresponds well to the glass transition temperature of ~ 195 K (see Table 1) for bulk $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ [2,151], which is in line with previous observations that the temperatures of phase changes in the macroscopic IL samples are in good agreement with phase changes in thin films on Ag(111) [81,94]. While bulk $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ has a melting temperature of 339 K, the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cations within the mixed thin film become mobile already at a much lower temperature[82]. This indicates that the mobility of the IL on top essentially determines the temperature at which the exchange at the IL/metal interface can occur.

In line with the conclusions derived above for the anion exchange[81], two main driving forces were suggested to be cooperatively responsible for

Figure 10. Top: F 1s and C 1s spectra in 0° and 80° emission for (a) clean Ag(111), (b) after deposition of 0.5 ML of [PFBMIm][PF₆] at 82 K, (c) after deposition of 1.0 ML of [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] on top of [PFBMIm][PF₆] at 82 K, and (d) after heating the composite IL film to RT. The arrows highlight changes in peak intensities compared to the respective spectrum below. Bottom left: Thermal evolution of the respective F 1s and C 1s signals from TP-XPS in 80° upon heating to RT. Bottom right: Molecular structures of the ILs. Adapted with permission from [82] under license CC BY 4.0.

the cation exchange at the IL/metal interface: a lower surface tension of [PFBMIm][PF₆] due to its fluorinated chain [152–154], favoring its enrichment at the IL/vacuum interface, and a larger adsorption energy of [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] on Ag(111) compared to [PFBMIm][PF₆] [82].

Surface destabilization and selective desorption

As discussed above, the WL of [PFBMIm][PF₆] partially decomposes on Ag(111) upon heating. Although the multilayer desorption of [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] partly overlaps with the desorption of [PFBMIm][PF₆], the latter can be desorbed intact within the multilayer desorption range from mixed

Figure 11. Scheme of selective replacement at the IL/metal interface and subsequent desorption of (a) [PFBMIm][PF₆] and (b) [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] after postdeposition of [C₈C₁Im][PF₆]. Adapted in part with permission from [81,82] under license CC BY 4.0.

thin films with [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] on Ag(111), leaving a WL of [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] behind, as sketched in Figure 11(a)[82]. In a similar fashion, it is possible to desorb [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N] selectively and entirely from mixed films with [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] already in the temperature range of multilayer desorption, see Figure 11(b)[81].

In both cases, the selective desorption is enabled by the selective replacement of the respective IL by [C₈C₁Im][PF₆] at the IL/Ag(111) interface and

the surface enrichment of $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cations and $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]^-$ anions in the respective mixtures [81,82]. In effect, it demonstrates that layers of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ directly adsorbed to the metal, can be destabilized by postdeposition of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ which opens new routes for selectively removing specific ions or undesired components at IL/support interfaces [81,82]. In principle, this procedure of sequential deposition and selective desorption should further allow for an on-surface metathesis of ILs with varying ion combinations that are not directly accessible by PVD (as for example alkyl imidazolium halides [93,155]).

Replacement of ionic liquids by porphyrins at metal interfaces

In analogy to molecular exchange and preferential adsorption processes after sequential deposition of two different ILs on Ag(111) [81,82], exchange processes have also been reported for organic bilayers on metals involving porphyrins and related aromatic molecules [156–164]. These investigations highlight the importance of the strength of the organic-metal interaction and its correlation to the stability and arrangement in stacked multilayer architectures [156,161,162,164–170]. Although combinations of porphyrins and ILs were already realized for catalysis [171] and dye-sensitized solar cell technologies [40,41], dedicated interface studies of porphyrin/IL hybrid systems are still missing. Porphyrins are a diverse and fascinating class of materials. Mimicking their vital role in numerous biological catalytic reactions and transport mechanisms [172,173], porphyrins also stimulated technical applications [174–181]. They offer great functional diversity through a vast degree of freedom concerning the variation of the substituents at the periphery of their tetrapyrrole core [83]. In the mentioned applications, the function, performance and stability of the composite thin films are strongly determined by the properties of the interface to the support [11,41,57,61–65,171]. To obtain some insights, we address temperature-dependent changes in the bilayer film structure of the IL $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and the 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin (2H-TPP, see Table 1) on Ag(111) and Au(111) in the following; see Figure 12 [83].

After deposition of 2H-TPP on top of 1 ML of frozen $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at 84 K, the 2H-TPP layer covers the IL film below. Heating this bilayer film subsequently to RT leads to a reorganization of the film at about 240 K, as determined by TP-XPS [83]. All intensities measured in 80° in Figure 12 remain mostly constant until the F_{PF_6} signal increases by almost 70%. Simultaneously, the C_{alkyl} signal of the $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+$ cation increases by more than 100%, while the porphyrin-related C 1s contribution decreases to 40%. This behavior indicates the exchange of the IL by the 2H-TPP molecules at the Ag(111) surface and the subsequent enrichment of

Figure 12. Left: Thermal evolution of F 1s and C 1s spectra measured in 80° during heating, after deposition of a monolayer of 2H-TPP on top of 1 ML of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ on Ag(111) at 84 K. Right: Scheme of the film structure upon sequential deposition at 84 K and after heating to RT. Adapted with permission from [83] under license CC BY 4.0.

$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at the IL/vacuum interface. Notably, composite films of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and 2H-TPP on Au(111) show the same behavior[83].

In the exchange studies of bilayered IL films discussed above, where $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ is initially at the vacuum interface [81,82], the onsets of diffusion are near the glass transition temperature of about ~195 K reported for bulk $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ [2,151]. The exchange of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ by 2H-TPP at the Ag(111) surface occurs, however, at a temperature that is about 50 K higher, which indicates that this process is determined rather by the properties of the porphyrin layer at the vacuum interface than the IL layer below, since $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ should already be liquid at a lower temperature. The shift of the exchange to considerably higher temperatures could result from a change in mobility of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ due to the confinement of the IL film under the 2H-TPP layer [83,182], which itself is likely stabilized laterally by strong phenyl-phenyl bonds [83,99,138,183–193]. In fact, Thussing *et al.* also reported in studies of organic bilayers a high thermal stability of the 2D-network of the top layer molecules due to strong intermolecular bonding, limiting the mobility of the molecules at the metal surface below [161,164]. Note, in contrast to the pure IL systems (Chapter 3.3), the IL film confined under the 2H-TPP layer shows no sign of molecular reorientation (*i.e.* alkyl chain enrichment) prior to the actual molecular exchange[83].

Since the exchange process is most likely driven by the larger adsorption energy of 2H-TPP at the metal surfaces compared to the IL[83], it is also

possible that the shift of the transition to higher T could be the result of a higher activation energy for the replacement of the IL by the porphyrin at the metal interface compared to the IL/IL films on Ag(111) [81,82].

As mentioned above, $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ desorbs from Ag(111) and Au(111) in two steps with multilayer desorption at 405 K and WL desorption at 445 K (see Table 3) [81–83]. If the metal surface is, however, covered by one closed layer of the porphyrin 2H-TPP, the entire IL film desorbs at 405 K, while the porphyrin monolayer remains[83]. The 2H-TPP layer acts as a spacer between $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and the metals and effectively seems to inhibit the specific interaction of the ions with the metal, leading to a pseudo-multilayer behavior of the $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ WL on 2H-TPP[83].

Our molecular-level UHV study on the replacement of the IL at the IL/metal interface after postdeposition of porphyrins helps understanding processes at liquid/solid interfaces in general, because it could be considered a model case of preferential adsorption of large molecules on surfaces from solutions. Compared to the deposition from the gas phase, the deposition from a liquid phase follows very different mechanisms and the resulting structures of the organic layer on the surface could be different [83,194].

Replacement effects of this kind are further related to stability concerns in IL-based catalysts. One example could be the poisoning of a SCILL system, where the adsorption of large molecular reactants might block the reactive sites on the surface, irreversibly lowering the catalytic activity over time, similar to poisoning of Pt catalysts by sulfur or other nonreactive species [60,195–198]. Another example would concern SILP systems based on large molecules (like metalloporphyrin derivatives) as catalytic centers[171]. It would cause major challenges if the catalyst complexes preferentially adsorb to the support surface and thus deplete from the liquid phase. The catalytic system would lose the characteristic homogeneous nature, possibly diminishing its reactivity/selectivity. From an even more general point of view, the observed exchange is also relevant for the stability of organic-organic heterostructures on solid supports. If, for example, a porphyrin-based electronic device is prepared at one temperature but used at higher temperatures, the increased mobility of the molecules could change the intended structure of the layered film stack.

Summary

The aim of this article was to present a concise overview of molecular-level studies addressing the adsorption, growth, stability and exchange phenomena of ILs on metal surfaces. We concentrated mostly on experimental data for a group of imidazolium-based ILs on single-crystalline Ag(111) and Au(111) surfaces, where an extensive data set is available, which serves as a basis for a detailed

comparison. The data was acquired by ARXPS in the group of the authors under identical experimental conditions. The findings were compared with results obtained by other groups in order to provide a comprehensive overview of literature on surface science studies of ILs on metal surfaces. The selected examples demonstrate the level of molecular insight, which can be achieved for specific systems. Where possible, we tried to deduce general trends. Altogether four different topics were addressed:

- (i) The adsorption and growth behavior of ILs on metal surfaces was studied. Variation in molecular structure and composition allowed for deriving certain structure-property relationships. The formation of a closed wetting layer appears to be one general similarity for ILs on metal surfaces, while the further growth on top of the wetting layer depends on the specific combination of IL and substrate.
- (ii) The desorption of ILs from metal surfaces plays a pivotal role for thin IL film applications at high temperature. While a longer alkyl chain length of otherwise identical imidazolium-based ILs leads to a considerably higher multilayer desorption temperature, the very similar desorption temperature of the remaining wetting layer indicates that the adsorption energy is dominated by the interaction of the ionic head groups with the substrate. The thorough discussion of the results for IL desorption with respect to literature studies provides a vantage point for obtaining a more comprehensive picture of the material properties at elevated temperatures.
- (iii) Ion exchange at the IL/solid interface and preferential enrichment of ions at the vacuum interface are observed after the sequential deposition of ultrathin films of two different ILs on Ag(111) at around 90 K and subsequent heating. The temperatures at which the exchange occurs appear to be related to the bulk glass transition temperature of the IL on top. Two driving forces are suggested to be responsible for the replacement at IL/solid interfaces, namely the tendency to minimize the surface free energy at the IL/vacuum interface and to maximize the adsorption energy at the IL/substrate interface. The results highlight how the interface compositions of ultrathin multi-component IL films depend on the combination of ions and how they can be controlled via temperature.
- (iv) The replacement of IL by porphyrins at metal interfaces was studied in light of the increasing interest in organic-organic multicomponent heterostructures. Porphyrins initially deposited on top of an IL below 90 K replace the IL at the IL/metal interface upon heating to above 240 K. This exchange process appears to be driven by the higher adsorption energy of porphyrin compared to the IL. Such

molecular-level UHV studies on the replacement of ILs by large organic molecules at IL/metal interfaces help understanding processes at liquid/solid interfaces in general.

As an outlook one might ask, to which extent the results obtained in the here-presented model studies in ultrahigh vacuum are transferable to real-world conditions, e.g. in catalysis. On the one hand, the low vapor pressure of the IL is one of the advantages of ILs that contribute to the known stability of thin films in SILP and SCILL applications, and also as protective layers for reactive substrates. On the other hand, especially the last example demonstrated that ILs can be replaced from the surface, e.g. by organic molecules. This is certainly one aspect that should receive more attention in the future. One particularly important coadsorbate to be investigated is water, since the relative humidity is an often uncontrolled parameter in applications. Here, detailed investigations are required to deduce further conclusions. Another factor influencing the adsorption and wetting properties could be the positive or negative curvature of the support in case of nanoparticles or nanopores, respectively. Very little is known on the molecular scale with respect to the formation of a wetting layer and further IL film growth for such curved supports, and future studies are highly desirable.

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